

A strategy for scalable data collection of soluble protein expression in diverse hosts

Project Goal:

Our goal is to stand-up an extensible experimental platform and standard data ontology for collecting large scale protein sequence-to-expression datasets in diverse host organisms.

- Methods are extensible to diverse host organisms, each with an organism-specific expression cassette.
- Pooled mass spectrometry will provide high-throughput data collection.
- The pooled method will be validated and supplemented by high-fidelity singleplex measurements using HiBit.

Contributors

Name	Affiliation	Proposal Role
Aljaž Gaber	University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Technology	Proposal Contributor
Ben Lehner	Center for Genomic Regulation	Proposal Contributor
Catherine Baranowski	Align to Innovate	Project Manager
Christopher Petzold	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory	Proposal Contributor
Christopher R. Reynolds	Eden Genetics Ltd	Proposal Contributor
David Ross	National Institute of Standards and Technology	Proposal Contributor
Diego A. Oyarzún	School of Informatics, University of Edinburgh School of Biological Sciences, University of Edinburgh	Proposal Contributor
Eli Bixby	Cradle Bio	Proposal Contributor
Elise de Reus	Cradle Bio	Proposal Contributor
Erika DeBenedictis	Align to Innovate	Leadership Team
Evangelos-Marios Nikolados	School of Biological Sciences, University of Edinburgh	Proposal Contributor
Hector Garcia Martin	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory DOE Joint BioEnergy Institute DOE Agile BioFoundry	Proposal Contributor
Howard Salis	Pennsylvania State University	Proposal Contributor
Michael C. Jewett	Department of Bioengineering, Stanford University	Proposal Contributor
Pete Kelly	Align to Innovate	Leadership Team
Sebastian Jaaks-Kraatz	Friedrich Miescher Institute for Biomedical Research	Proposal Contributor
Swati Choudhary	Formerly at Shiru, Inc.	Proposal Contributor

Proposal Summary

Recombinant protein expression is central to academic exploration as well as biotechnology's advancement of human health, climate applications and the bioeconomy in general. However, not all proteins can be expressed in all organisms, and the field lacks a predictive model of soluble protein expression that could replace laborious experimental trial-and-error. **This project aims to design and test an extensible experimental platform and standardized data ontology for collecting soluble recombinant protein expression data across organisms.** The resulting dataset will be used in building increasingly generalizable predictive models of protein expression.

In this document, we have roadmapped data collection techniques, designed experiments to assess their feasibility, and outlined a proof-of-concept pilot study that would be conducted prior to full-scale data acquisition (Figure 1). Here, we propose a [plan of action](#) that will establish the feasibility

of gathering ML-ready soluble protein expression data in two organisms commonly-used in biomanufacturing and protein expression: *Escherichia coli* and *Pichia pastoris*. Results of the feasibility study will inform decisions about the specifics of future pilot and full-scale data acquisition. We encourage the reader to reference our review, "[Can protein expression be 'solved'?](#)"¹ for details on soluble protein expression.

Once gathered, the dataset proposed here will adhere to FAIR principals², be publically available, and "living" – researchers can freely use it and it will continue to grow over time. Subsequent experiments (beyond those outlined in this proposal) will include examining more protein sequences and expression in different organisms (e.g. *Bacillus subtilis*, *Aspergillus niger*) to make the model more extensible.

Definitions

Strains:

Ec = *Escherichia coli*

Pp = *Pichia pastoris* (*Komagataella phaffii*)

Bs = *Bacillus subtilis*

Measurements:

- **Soluble protein expression:** measurable recombinant protein present in the soluble fraction of cell lysate, specifically produced in the context of a microbial expression system (e.g. *E.coli*)
- **Singleplex expression assay (SPX):** An arrayed measurement of protein expression measured in cells or cell lysate. Results from singleplex expression measurements can be used to calibrate large-scale, pooled expression measurements, or on their own as standalone quantification. Examples include HiBIT, split fluorescent protein (split-FP), Pierce BCA
- **Pooled expression assay:** A multiplexed measurement of protein quantity in a mixed population of cells, each expressing a distinct ORF. Examples include growth based assays³⁻⁵, SortSeq⁶⁻⁹ and peptide flycodes¹⁰.
- **Controls:** samples with a known output. In our SPX assay an example of a control would be a protein with a known level of expression in the same genetic cassette and strain.

- **Calibration:** comparing to a known standard to remove technical variation between runs (for example, drift of an instrument). In our SPX assay an example of calibration would be to measure a known standard.
- **Normalization:** comparing your assay readout to a measurable quantity to remove variation between samples. In our SPX assay, each well's protein quantification could be normalized to its OD so that you can compare between samples with lower and higher growth but control for the number of cells producing the protein.

Genetic Components:

- **Open reading frame (ORF):** "The protein-coding region(s) of each mRNA is composed of a contiguous, non overlapping string of codons called an open reading frame (commonly known as an ORF). Each ORF specifies a single protein and starts and ends at internal sites within the mRNA."¹¹

What factors impact soluble protein expression?

A major challenge in studying protein expression is that there are many different mechanisms by which a protein can fail to properly express (Figure 2). Broadly the factors that impact expression can be divided into two categories^{16,17} (Figure 3):

1. Extrinsic factors that represent experimental choices in how to express the protein - host genotype, expression cassette architecture, and experimental details of culturing, lysis etc - that can be modified for better results.

2. Intrinsic factors that are driven by the specific amino acid sequence - foldability, stability and solubility - and cannot be altered without changing the identity of the protein.

Our dataset proposes to explore both extrinsic (different host organisms) and intrinsic factors (different amino acid sequences) to produce reproducible, quantitative measurements of soluble expression. Ideally, the impact of both intrinsic and extrinsic factors can be predicted using machine learning models that are trained on the resulting dataset.

Figure 3: Intrinsic and extrinsic factors contributing to soluble protein expression.

Plan of action

We propose to move toward large, living datasets of soluble protein expression in diverse organisms with the following three step plan:

1. Establish **feasibility** of data collection. This ~\$500K, 9-month project will serve as a proof-of-concept that data can be collected and will determine the quality, throughput, and price point. An additional \$200K has been allocated for follow-up feasibility experiments if necessary.
2. **Pilot** data acquisition. This phase will apply the de-risked data collection methods to gather a small amount of data in two organisms, thus providing preliminary data for ML modeling and guiding expansion. The length and cost of this phase will be determined based on the assay promoted from feasibility.
3. **Full-scale** data acquisition. During this phase, the dataset will be expanded both in number of organisms* and the number of proteins measured.

*For additional organisms, feasibility and pilot phases will be repeated to ensure applicability of methods.

The first round of experimentation will focus on carrying *Escherichia coli* (Ec) and *Pichia pastoris* (Pp) through the assay feasibility, pilot and full-scale experimentation pipeline (Figure 4). Stage gates allow data-driven decision making for the next step in our pipeline. Following the first round of experimentation, subsequent organism feasibility studies for SPX and pooled assay would be focused on the assay(s) promoted in round 1.

Feasibility

Feasibility encompasses building and using strains expressing control ORFs with known expression to test methods for protein expression. Feasibility will provide concrete values for the cost and time per sample for the assays tested. In total, our proposed feasibility study involves testing two singleplex methods against a standard set of 30 ORFs (Table 1).

This feasibility study is a precursor to developing a higher-throughput, pooled method. If the proposed feasibility study is successful, we will use the control strains and SPX data as a foundation for method development of a pooled assay.

Assays

To identify SPX and pooled assay candidates, we assessed methods used in previous large scale data collection efforts, and alternative methods that could be amenable for collection of this dataset (see Review for details). A summary of this assessment can be found in Table 2 below. We have determined that a SPX assay will be necessary as a validation assay, or if scalable could be used for a pilot-scale experiment. Therefore, we will start feasibility with SPX assay development, and we provide more details on the SPX assay options we considered in Table 3.

We will first test two SPX assays: HiBiT and mass spectrometry. These were chosen for SPX feasibility because they have small tags, the readouts are proportional to protein expression, they require limited optimization, and they are easily extended to other organisms (important for future dataset growth). Use of a fluorescent protein tag has not been ruled out, rather it may be a second tier option if HiBiT and mass spectrometry do not show promising results.

Potential pooled methods to be tested in feasibility are included in Table 2. It is important to note that assays that are marked with a red "x" in the "Assay" column (x) will not be considered for dataset collection due to issues with adaptability with other organisms (Cell-free, YSD, TAT) or method sharing hurdles (peptide flycodes). Currently, label-free proteomics and SortSeq are the pooled assays most likely to be pursued in feasibility following successful SPX method development.

Assays	Strains	Genetic cassette	Control ORFs	Unique sample number
HiBiT	<i>E. coli</i> BL21 AI <i>F-ompT hsdSB (rB-, mB-) gal dcm araB::T7RNAP-tetA</i>	pET28a IPTG + arabinose inducible expression	18 diverse ORFs from Boel et al ¹⁸ . 12 codon varied mScarlet13 ¹⁹ .	30 ORFs will be cloned with both N- and C-terminal HiBiT tags = 60 total unique samples
Mass spectrometry	<i>P. pastoris</i> OPENPichia NCYC 2543 hoc1tr-1	Integration at AOX1 methanol inducible expression	The same 30 ORFs will be cloned into pET28a for Ec expression, or integrated at AOX1 for Pp expression.	30 ORFs will be cloned with both N- and C-terminal his tags = 60 total unique samples

Table 1: Details of Feasibility Design.

Figure 4: Steps and stage-gates for first round of dataset collection.

	Assay	Reproducible	Shareable	Scalable	Quick/easy to run and analyze	Affordable	Adaptability to other expression systems	+/-
SPX	HiBit Total = 14	✓✓ Kit-based, lysis variability	✓✓✓	✓✓ Plate-based, SPX	✓✓ Growth, lysis, kit-based reaction, readout	✓✓ Kit <\$1/sample	✓✓ HiBit tag, lysis troubleshooting	+ easy, commonly used method industrially, kit-based - cell lysis and reaction timing may require troubleshooting
	Mass spectrometry Total = 15	✓✓✓ Common method	✓✓✓	✓✓ Plate-based, MS instrument time, SPX	✓✓✓ Common methods	✓ Ni-NTA for pull downs, MS time	✓✓✓ His tag + protein extraction	+ adaptable, common "gold standard" method - costly
	Split-FP Total = 16	✓✓✓ Plate reader protocol	✓✓✓	✓✓ Plate-based, SPX	✓✓✓ Growth, readout	✓✓✓ Plate reader time	✓ FP expression, requires tuning	+ easy, commonly used - FP expression tuning
	Coomassie SDS-PAGE (+/- Ni-NTA)	✓✓ Lysis variability	✓✓✓	X Some steps not plate based	✓ Many steps involved	✓ Ni NTA for purification, cost of people time	✓✓✓ His tag + protein extraction	+ adaptable, common "gold standard" method - low throughput, time intensive
Pooled	Label-free proteomics Total = 12	✓✓ Newly adopted method	✓✓✓	✓✓ pool size limitation, MS time	✓? Pool size limitation, requires protocol and analysis development	✓ Ni-NTA for pull downs, MS time, pooled, depends on pool sizes	✓✓✓	+ adaptable, common "gold standard" method - low throughput, time intensive
	SortSeq Total = 13	✓✓ FACS method/analysis	✓✓✓	✓✓✓ FACS time	✓✓ Growth, readout, FACS + sequencing	✓✓ Pooled, FACS time	✓ FP expression, tuning, FACS methods at facilities may be limiting	+ pooled, mostly adaptable - FP expression tuning; FACS method and analysis onboarding / development
	Growth based assay (DHFR) Total = 13	✓✓ Antibiotic selection	✓✓✓	✓✓✓ automatable NGS methods	✓? Growth, antibiotic selection, sequencing	✓✓✓ Pooled, NGS	? Requires specific antibiotic sensitivity	+ affordable, pooled - indirect readout, adaptability unknown, uncommon assay for expression, large tag on ORF required
	Peptide flycodes	? New method and analysis pipeline	X method sharing prohibited	? Large pools possible, MS method time	✓? Pooled growth, new method and analysis pipeline	✓ Pooled, MS time, method dev1 cost	✓✓✓ Peptide tag on ORF and protein extractions	+ adaptable, pooled - new method with unclear chance of success, non trivial data analysis and design, not a shareable method
	Cell-Free Protease assay	? An existing method moved to a cell free system	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	X Cell free	+ affordable and quick - not commonly used, cell-free
	YSD+FACS	✓✓ FACS method/analysis	✓✓✓	✓✓ FACS time	✓✓ Growth, staining, readout, FACS + sequencing	✓✓ Pooled, FACS time, stain	X Yeast only	+ easy, commonly used - yeast specific, requires protein export to cell surface
TAT+FACS	✓✓ Antibiotic selection	✓✓✓	✓✓✓ automatable NGS methods	✓? Growth, antibiotic selection, sequencing	✓✓✓ Pooled, NGS	X Ecoli only	+ easy - E.coli specific, requires protein export	

Table 2: Assay Assessment. The total listed in the "Assay" column refers to the number of check marks per row. Details for SPX assays are in Table 3, and details for pooled assays are in Supplemental Table 1. The yellow box highlights the first two assays chosen for feasibility studies in *Ec* and *Pp*.

Assay	Tag size (a.a)	Readout	Organisms	Extensibility	Optimization	Equipment needed	Notes
HiBIT	11 HiBIT peptide tag	Luminescence proportional to quantity of protein	<i>E. coli</i> * <i>P. pastoris</i> * <i>B. subtilis</i> ²⁰ HEK293T ^{21,22} Cell-Free ²³ <i>A. niger</i> ²⁴	Any organism that can be lysed in a manner compatible with detection reagents, including cell-free.	Cell lysis, timing of enzymatic readout, background proteins that can activate LgBit and cause signal without NanoBit	luminometer, sonicator for cell lysis	Mechanical lysis (Bead beating) followed by use of the extracellular detection kit has been cited in lactic acid bacteria ²⁵ and budding yeast S288c ²⁶ . Used for protein transport assays in bacteria ²⁷⁻³⁰ and for pathogen detection via phage ³¹ however these either did not require lysis or utilize phage for cell lysis. <i>*used industrially</i>
Mass spec	6-8 his tag	protein abundance	<i>E. coli</i> ³² <i>P. pastoris</i> ³³ <i>B. subtilis</i> ³⁴ CHO ³⁵ HEK293T ³⁶ Cell-Free ^{37,38} <i>A. niger</i> ³⁹	Any organism that proteins can be extracted from.	Protein extraction and instrument settings	Mass spectrometer	
Split FP assay	16 FP split	Fluorescence is proportional to the quantity of protein. Constitutive expression of another FP may be important for relative abundance (extrinsic noise)	<i>E. coli</i> ^{40,41} <i>P. pastoris</i> ⁴² <i>B. subtilis</i> ⁴³ CHO ^{44,45} HEK293T ^{40,46} Cell-Free ^{47,48} <i>A. niger</i> ⁴⁹	Any organism that fluorescent proteins can reliably be expressed and measured in.	expression of constitutive FP fragment, background fluorescence (growth conditions)	plate reader	Used a plate reader instead of FACS in <i>Pichia</i> , used flow cytometry without sorting in <i>B. subtilis</i> ,

Table 3: SPX assay details.

General Experimental Workflow

The experimental workflow for feasibility of HiBiT and mass spectrometry is assay independent. In fact, the same basic steps for sample generation would be used across most assays. Figure 5 below details the general experimental workflow and highlights points at which samples would be taken for different SPX and potential pooled assays. Strains would first be built (steps 1-2, transformation with the organism specific expression cassette and selection for proper transformation), then grown for protein production (step 3, this would include induction of the expression cassette and could be performed in plates for SPX or flasks for pooled methods). After protein expression, the cells would be lysed and the sample would be centrifuged to separate the soluble from the insoluble fraction. As we are interrogating only soluble protein expression, the soluble fraction would be used for HiBiT or mass spectrometry to measure target protein expression.

Organism specific strains and expression cassettes

For each organism that will be used during feasibility, we have selected a single strain and an organism specific expression cassette. We have chosen commonly used strains and genetic cassettes for both *E. coli* and *P. pastoris*. Table 4 details the specific strains we will use for feasibility.

Strain	Key Features
<i>E. coli</i> BL21-AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • F-<i>ompT</i> hsdSB (rB-, mB-) <i>gal dcm araB::T7RNAP-tetA</i> • Arabinose-inducible T7 RNA polymerase expression • Fast growth- Doubling time ~20 minutes • Protease deficient (<i>lon</i> and <i>ompT</i>)
<i>P. pastoris</i> (<i>Komagataella phaffii</i>) OPENPichia <i>his4</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genome sequenced type strain derived from NCYC 2543 (NCYC 2543 hoc1tr-1) • Near-identical to NRRL Y-11430, the commercialized and difficult to license industrial strain • <i>Hoc1</i> truncation increases transformation efficiency up to NYYL Y-11430 • Doubling time ~60-120 minutes • Open-access strain and cloning materials

Table 4: Details of strains to be used in feasibility.

E. coli Strain and Expression Cassette

There are many available strains of *E. coli* designed for various protein expression purposes. Some engineered characteristics include protease deficiency (BL21 lon and ompT), IPTG induction of genes driven by a phage T7 promoter (BL21(DE3)), gene mutations to help with cytosolic disulfide bond formation (SHuffle T7, Origami2), and addition of tRNAs for rare codons to improve expression of genes with rare codons (Rosetta2)^{50,51}. This dataset will begin with the BL21(DE3) related strain, BL21-AI. Strain BL21-AI is closely related to BL21(DE3). The primary difference is the T7 RNA polymerase expression. In BL21-AI, the native *araB* gene was replaced with the *araBAD* promoter driving T7 RNA polymerase, and marked with a tetracycline resistance marker (Δ *araB*::T7RNAPol-tetA)^{52,53}. BL21(DE3) contains the λ DE3 lysogen that contains T7 RNA polymerase gene under control of the *lacUV5* promoter.⁵⁴

There are many available plasmids for protein expression in *Ec*, with over 100 of these belonging to the pET vector series (plasmid for expression by T7 RNA polymerase). “These expression plasmids support high levels of transcription in strains of *Escherichia coli* that contain a lysogenised DE3 phage fragment encoding the T7 RNA polymerase and they have become a workhorse for the scientific community...The pET plasmid series is the most popular when compared to alternatives, such as the pGEX, pQE or pBAD plasmids. pET vectors have a total of 220,000 entries in the publication record. Of the pET plasmids, pET28a-c is the most widely used, recording over 50,000 recorded entries, of which *pET28a alone accounts for 40,000 entries.*”⁵⁵. Given its dominance in the protein expression field, expression of target proteins in *Ec* will use the pET28 plasmid backbone.

Figure 6: Expression cassette in BL21-AI.

P. pastoris Strain and Expression Cassette

Pichia has been widely adopted in industry for protein expression, and excels at secreted protein production due to the organism's very high growth density. Additionally its limited secretome allows for a purer yield and minimizes downstream purification⁵⁶. Commonly used strains like GS115 (histidine auxotroph) are derived from difficult to license strains. Recently, an open-source strain (OPEN*Pichia*) has been sequenced, phenotype and made available⁵⁷. "The most common approach for heterologous protein expression in *P. pastoris* is the insertion of the target gene into the genome under the control of the AOX1 (alcohol oxidase 1) promoter (pAOX1). This approach offers tight regulation and a very strong, methanol-inducible expression"⁵⁸. It is important to note that genetic engineering in *Pichia* comes with some drawbacks that are less common in

other microbes. Clonal variation is observed in the transformant population both in integration copy number and non-specific integration⁵⁹. A multiple integration could lead to significant range in expression of a target protein, and there are strategies to select for multiple integrations to increase yields⁶⁰.

Both episomal and integrative plasmids exist for heterologous gene expression in Pp; however, integration of expression cassettes is preferred since episomal plasmids are not stably maintained⁶¹. The general strategy is to linearize and transform an integrative vector so that it integrates into the genome at the locus corresponding to the homology arms on the plasmid (Figure 7). **We will be integrating expression ORFs at the commonly used AOX1 promoter, leading to methanol inducible expression of the target protein.**

Figure 7: *Pichia* expression cassette. Figure adapted from⁵⁶.

Control ORFs

For feasibility, we will use 2 sets of control ORFs- a diverse ORF expression ladder and a fluorescent protein sequence that has been codon varied multiple times to produce many variants. The goal of the diverse ORF expression ladder is to test ORFs with known levels of expression in *Ec* from a pET vector using our SPX methods. We want to compare our SPX data to the published expression data. If the data validates against the published expression rankings, we would be able to use this ladder as controls for subsequent pooled assay development and pilot experiments. It is important to note that

this set of ORFs has an unknown expression in Pp. However, we hypothesize that there will be a range of expression since the ORFs are sourced from a wide range of organisms. We also included a codon varied fluorescent protein ORF set. There is literature precedent that shows that a range of expression can be produced by simply varying codon usage for a FP in the target organism⁶². We will not know the expression of these FPs in *Ec* and Pp until we run the experiment, however fluorescence provides a quick orthogonal readout to HiBiT and mass spectrometry therefore we feel these ORFs are valuable to include.

ORF set	Purpose	Pro	Con
Diverse ORF expression ladder (Boel <i>et al</i>)	Ladder of diverse ORFs from literature with range of expression in <i>Ec</i> . Does SPX recapitulate known ladder of expression?	Validated expression in <i>Ec</i> , sequence variation tests protein length and diversity in assay context.	Assay failure may be due to difference in ORF seq and not method. Unknown expression in Pp.
Codon varied fluorescent protein (mScarlet13)	Predict that there will be a range of expression after varying codon usage to generate a ladder of expression from unchanged amino acid sequence.	Fluorescence provides a quick orthogonal readout to HiBiT, easy to design and order. ORF is the same size and function - controlled.	No <i>a priori</i> expression levels to benchmark against.

Table 5: Summary of Control ORFs for Feasibility.

Pilot

Though the focus of this document is the feasibility phase of the project, high-level planning for pilot and full-scale experiments is underway to mitigate risk and shorten the timeline for these phases. The goal of the pilot is to use our assays on larger numbers of ORFs after they have been

validated and promoted from feasibility. The pilot can be thought of as the “proof-of-concept” after feasibility of assays is determined. More information on potential pilot DNA can be found in [Supplemental Table 2](#) and [3](#).

Full-scale

The full-scale experiments build upon the pilot’s foundation and expand scope to specific protein waves in Ec and Pp. If the pilot is deemed successful, the full-scale experiment will be launched. Here, we aim to test specific waves of proteins. We propose to expand upon the pilot with more diverse ORFs.

Second, synthesized gene variants could be tested. And third, newly designed proteins to challenge and validate our models would be run. Suggestions for target proteins can be found in [Supplemental Table 3](#).

	Feasibility	Pilot	Full-scale
Stage Gates	<p>Stage gate 1: Go/No-Go for pooled assay development in Ec and Pp</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SPX assay development completed 2. Data review to determine which SPX assay to promote as “gold-standard” for dataset 3. Data review from SPX assay to determine go/no-go for pooled assay development <p>Stage gate 2: Go/No-Go for Pilot in Ec and Pp</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pooled assay development completed 2. Data review to determine which pooled assay to promote 3. Comparison of SPX and pooled assay to determine if pilot-scale data collect is feasible with either assay 	<p>Stage gate 3: Go/No-Go for full-scale experimentation in Ec and Pp</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pilot experiments completed 2. Pilot data review to determine whether experimental design of pilot should be used for full-scale experimentation 3. Feasibility of full-scale experimentation 	<p>Stage gate 4: Go/No-Go for feasibility in next organism (proposed organism - <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> - Bs)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Full-scale experiments completed 2. Review of full-scale experimental data for Ec and Pp 3. Feasibility of onboarding subsequent organism- Cost, time and accessibility (identification of partners that can work with <i>B. subtilis</i>)
Deliverables	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. SPX assay experimental and analysis methods. 2. Protein expression data for control ORFs in Ec and Pp using SPX assay(s). 3. SPX assay selection for “gold-standard” quantification. 4. Decision on whether pooled assay development is launched. If SPX assay development is deemed successful, pooled method development to start (“Go” at Stage Gate 1). 5. Pooled assay experimental and analysis methods. 6. Protein expression data for control ORF pools in Ec and Pp using a pooled assay 7. Decision on whether SPX or pooled assay can be used for pilot-scale experiments (Go/No-Go at Stage Gate 2). 8. Freely available data and methods 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Protein expression data for ~10,000 ORFs in Ec and Pp using the assay promoted from the feasibility phase. 2. Assay assessment for full-scale experiments (time, cost, data quality) 3. Decision on whether experimental strategy can be promoted to full-scale experiments (Go/No-Go at Stage Gate 3) 4. Data used to generate models of expression in Ec and Pp. 5. Freely available data and methods. 6. Publication of results in a peer-reviewed journal. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Protein expression data for ~200,000 ORFs in Ec and Pp using the same assay that was used in the pilot. 2. Decision on whether experimental strategy can be extended to the next organism. 3. Data used to generate predictive models of expression in Ec and Pp. 4. Freely available data and methods. 5. Publication of results in a peer-reviewed journal.
Success Criteria	<p>The SPX assay must satisfy the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data gathered validates against known expression of control ORFs (the expression “ladder”). • The ladder performs reproducibly, and the dynamic range of the expression ladder is characterized to define the limits of the assay. • Process variation is described and increments of resolution based on the data are determined. • Required replicate structure is determined. • Data can be expressed as [assay value] per cell (the assay value depends on what the specific assay measures). • Methods and analysis pipelines must be shareable. <p>The pooled assay must satisfy the following criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data gathered validates against known expression of control ORFs (the expression “ladder”) and the SPX data using the same strains. • The ladder pool performs reproducibly, and the dynamic range of the expression ladder is characterized to define the limits of the assay. • Process variation is described and increments of resolution based on the data are determined. • Required replicate structure is determined. • Data can be expressed as [assay value] per cell (the assay value depends on what the specific assay measures). • Methods and analysis pipelines must be shareable. 	<p>The pilot experiments in Ec and Pp must satisfy the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data must be generated at N=2 sites for at least one of the organisms • Control strain performance during pilot must replicate SPX assay performance during feasibility • If a pooled assay is used, 10% of the strains tested for each organism must be tested with the validated SPX assay and this data must be consistent with the pilot assay data for these strains • Models generated from the data show predictive power • We have to be able to learn about how many data points are needed for the full-scale experiments to build the best model (performance probably tops out and then more data is not being used for the model) 	

Table 6: Stage gates, deliverables and success criteria per phase.

Machine learning analysis strategy

The purpose of this project is not to develop and train machine learning models for predicting protein expression, but rather to showcase that this dataset enables such an approach. We invite members of the research community to use this data for their own model development.

Calculating quantitative protein abundance and storing metadata

Data will be composed of protein DNA sequence and corresponding protein abundance. Protein abundance calculations will be assay specific, and will be explored during feasibility. Metadata will involve host, plasmid sequence information, culturing and lysing details as well as protocol information (Figure 8).

Data Schema

Our preliminary data schema (Figure 8) outlines a structure whose purpose it is to handle all data generated by the sequence to expression platform. During feasibility, the schema will be matured and expanded.

“The goal is to create a structure that is flexible enough to accommodate different *expression hosts and ORFs*, and labs with different instruments, yet standardized enough to be easily parsable for ML. Along with the datasets, we will develop the protocols produced in a machine readable form, since these datasets will be later processed by artificial intelligence or ML applications advanced enough to understand the procedures.”⁶³

Data quality check (QC)

Data quality will be tested through the following automated pipelines:

1. File integrity check.
2. Outlier detection and elimination.

3. Missing data detection (e.g. sequences without protein expression, missing partial sequences).
4. Comparison between singleplex and multiplex data for the same protein.
5. Test length is above minimum (100 amino acids) and below maximum (1000 amino acids).
6. Reproducibility of control data.
7. Reproducibility of sample data collected on two separate days.

Though not automated, another check of the experimentally derived data would be the comparison of expression levels to those reported in literature (where possible).

Data Storage

Data will be made available in an Align-hosted database accessible to the public through a REST API (in a structure similar to the [Experiment Data Depot](#)⁶⁴). For longevity and redundancy of data, snapshots of this database at certain time points (e.g., for the initial data set, or for large data increases) may be duplicated to a 3rd party repository (e.g., [Nature Scientific Data](#)⁶⁵ or Zenodo).

Proposed methods for data evaluation

Quality of experimental data will be checked by calculating the R^2 of data gathered on two separate days. High quality data would show high R^2 .

Predictive performance will be evaluated by partitioning data into train-test split partitions based on a selected molecular property, using a framework such as Spectra⁶⁶. For instance, borrowing from the distinction between extrinsic and intrinsic properties, we could create various Spectra-based train-test splits, encode/embed with different methods, and train different models of increasing complexity⁶⁷.

Figure 8: Preliminary Data Schema.

First steps and ultimate goal

In this proposal we are detailing the feasibility phase of two organisms including potential directions for a pilot phase. Based on feasibility, we will formulate a detailed plan for future experimentation in these organisms. The goal of this section is to outline the vision for the growth of this dataset beyond our proposal.

Unique aspects of our final target dataset:

- Abide by the principles of reproducible, shareable, scalable to enable use by scientists across fields and sectors
- Collect >1M points across broad protein families
- Expression of the same proteins in several organisms to be compared side-by-side
- Perform experiments *in vivo* rather than *in vitro*
- Generate “ML-ready” data and metadata that is freely available via API access and provided in a standardized and consistent experimental format(s)

Dataset expansion dimensions

We envision that this dataset will grow and expand in multiple directions to understand how commonly variables in protein expression impact recovery of soluble protein (Figure 9).

- Different host organisms and different genotypes of each host (protease deficient, disulfide bond promoting etc)
- More protein sequences (waves of diverse, deep mutational scanning, and *de novo* proteins suggested)
- Additional experimental conditions (temperature, media, growth vessel...)
- Changing the expression cassettes (promoters for expression, solubility tags etc.)
- Targeted localization of protein: Secreted vs intracellular expression
- Collecting different types of data- Analysis of failure modes (quantifying RNA, measurement of insoluble fraction, +/- chaperones)

Summary

- Industrial production, basic science exploration and scientific tool development are all examples of fields that would benefit from the models that will be generated based on this sequence-to-expression dataset.
- We are starting with *E. coli* and *P. pastoris* because these will produce valuable datasets for both academia and industry and are easier to work with than other expression systems.
- There is no assay that stands out as a clear winner, therefore we are running feasibility on a few assays to determine which will be the best to move forward with.
- Once feasibility identifies assay(s) that can be scaled for the pilot, we will run the pilot in *E. coli* and *P. pastoris* testing diverse ORFs. Pilot DNA needs to be economical, diverse and amenable to cloning into Ec and Pp expression cassettes.
- Full-scale experimental directions are to be determined but waves of specific designed ORFs are under consideration.

Supplemental material

Supplemental table 1: Citations of pooled assay use in protein expression systems of interest.

Assay	Tag size (a.a)	Readout	Organisms	Extensibility	Optimization	Equipment needed	Notes
Label-free proteomics	6-8 his tag	Relative protein abundance via mass spectrometry	<i>E. coli</i> ²² <i>P. pastoris</i> ³³ <i>B. subtilis</i> ³⁴ HEK293T ³⁶ Cell-Free ³⁸ <i>A. niger</i> ³⁹	Any organism that proteins can be extracted from.	Size of pools possible, strategy of pooling ORFs to maximize tryptic peptide diversity, data analysis of target ORFs, input calibration standards.	Mass spectrometer	
SortSeq	16 FP split	Cells sorted by fluorescence (expression) into bins, and abundance of strain/bin enumerated via NGS	<i>E. coli</i> ^{6,8,70,71} <i>P. pastoris</i> <i>B. subtilis</i> ⁷² CHO ⁷³ HEK293T ⁷⁴ Cell-Free <i>A. niger</i> ⁷⁵	Any organism that a split-FP**can be expressed and measured in, and that FACS and downstream NGS can be performed on.	Expression of constitutive FP fragment, background fluorescence, cell sorting protocol, data analysis	FACS, sequencer	Most citations are not utilizing a split-FP for Sort-Seq. A. niger SortSeq utilized Flow-cytometry but not FACS.
Growth based assay (DHFR)	81 DHFR[3] split	Following selection, abundance of each strain is enumerated via NGS and compared to the starting population.	<i>E. coli</i> ⁷⁶⁻⁷⁸ <i>P. pastoris</i> <i>B. subtilis</i> CHO HEK293T Cell-Free <i>A. niger</i>	Any organism sensitive to trimethoprim, methotrexate or other DHFR targeting compound.	Amount of selective pressure, expression of constitutive DHFR [1,2] fragment	sequencer	For E.coli, other antibiotics have been used before, though not in a split-format necessarily ^{79,80,81} . DHFR gene exists in Pp ^{82,83} . B. subtilis is known to be trimethoprim sensitive ⁸⁴ . In CHO cells, DHFR used for gene amplification in DHFR null CHO cell line ⁷³ . Most literature using DHFR growth-based assay is in <i>S. cerevisiae</i> ^{4,5,85} .
Peptide flycodes	11-15 peptide barcode	Flycode abundance via mass spectrometry	<i>E. coli</i> ⁸⁶ <i>P. pastoris</i> <i>B. subtilis</i> CHO HEK293T Cell-Free <i>A. niger</i>	Any organism that proteins can be extracted from.	Flycode sequences, technical method for extracting flycodes, method for running flycodes on MS, data analysis	Orbitrap mass spectrometer	

Supplemental Table 2: Potential Pilot and Full-scale Experiments

Pilot and full-scale experiments will not begin until feasibility has been established.

The information below outlines potential directions for these follow-up experiments.

Project phase	Protein Wave	Details	Source of sequences	Number of sequences	Organism specific?
Feasibility	Controls	To cover a range of expression in organism specific circuit	Synthesis	30	Yes
Pilot		Diverse ORFs	To be purchased. Existing ORF libraries an option.	10,000	No, to be expressed in all expression systems
Full-scale experiment	Wave 1 broad protein landscape	Diverse ORFs	ORF libraries, cDNA capture from metagenomic samples	200,000	expression of constitutive FP fragment, background fluorescence (growth conditions)
	Wave 2 deep protein variant scan	20 genes x 10,000 variants of each	Existing deep mutational scanning library or oligo based ORF mutations	200,000	
	Wave 3 design proteins	Designed/Predicted/Intentional to validate our model	Synthesis	200,000	

Supplemental Table 3: Potential Pilot DNA

The goal of the pilot experiment is to test the platform developed in feasibility with expression of a few thousand ORFs. Ideally, these ORFs would be diverse in origin and sequence, easy and economical to obtain and amenable to cloning into Ec and Pp expression cassettes. Some options being considered to source pilot DNA include ORF and/or cDNA libraries cloned into organism specific expression vectors. These ORFs will be expressed in all organisms (starting with Ec and Pp). We plan to quantify the diversity score between ORFs chosen to understand how much sequence space is covered in our pilot experiment.

Number of Sequences	Origin organism	Notes on DNA	Link to Library
3974	<i>E.coli</i>	open reading frame (ORFeome) collection of 3974 or 94% of the known Escherichia coli K-12 ORFs in Gateway entry vector pENTR/Zeo	https://shigen.nig.ac.jp/ecoli/strain/resource/gatewayEntryCloneLibrary/about
4,956	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (yeast)	MOBY Orf 1.0 -The molecular barcoded yeast open reading frame (MoBY-ORF) library was initially created to provide insight into identifying drug resistance mutations in yeast. Through the use of MoBY-ORF complementation cloning, spontaneous drug-resistant mutants can be identified via depletion of a unique molecular barcode. These barcodes permit use of a pooled screening strategy as well as simultaneous measurement of all transformants.	https://horizondiscovery.com/en/non-mammalian-research-tools/products/molecular-barcoded-yeast-moby-orf-library
12,085	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i> (plant)	Collection: Arabidopsis thaliana Collection V 1 (Gateway Entry Vectors)	https://dnasu.org/DNASU/GetCollection.do?collectionName=Arabidopsis%20thaliana%20Collection%20V%201%20(Gateway%20Entry%20Vectors)
10,268	<i>Drosophila</i> (fruit fly)	Collection: FlyBi Drosophila ORFeome vFB5.52	https://dnasu.org/DNASU/GetCollection.do?collectionName=FlyBi%20Drosophila%20ORFeome%20vFB5.52
1,202	<i>Thermotoga Maritima</i> (thermophilic bacterium)	Collection: Thermotoga Maritima Plasmid collection (in pMH bacterial expression vectors)	https://dnasu.org/DNASU/GetCollection.do?collectionName=Thermatoga%20Maritima%20Plasmid%20collection%20(in%20pMH%20bacterial%20expression%20vectors)
11,000	<i>C.elegans</i>	The C. elegans ORF collection (also known as the C. elegans ORFeome) was created as a resource for functionally characterizing the worm proteome through applications, such as protein-protein interactions, RNAi, and protein expression in Caenorhabditis elegans. Generated in the laboratory of Marc Vidal by amplification from full-length cDNA libraries and cloned into the Gateway-donor vector pDONR201, the C. elegans ORF clones can be easily moved into any expression vector via recombinational cloning.	https://horizondiscovery.com/en/non-mammalian-research-tools/products/c-elegans-orf-collection
8,667	<i>Xenopus</i> (frog)	Collection: Xenopus ORFeome Collection	https://dnasu.org/DNASU/GetCollection.do?collectionName=Thermatoga%20Maritima%20Plasmid%20collection%20(in%20pMH%20bacterial%20expression%20vectors)

Suggested further reading

There are a few papers that we recommend for further context:

This proposed dataset platform is part of Align’s Open Dataset Initiative, which pioneers new ways to identify, collect, and share large datasets in life science. Read more about the Open Datasets initiative here:

“What Biology Can Learn from Physics”, December 2023, Asimov Press.

This proposal builds upon a roadmapping effort summarized in our review, “Can protein expression be ‘solved?’”, which provides more detail on the available methods for gathering protein expression data and precedent for building predictive models.

“Can protein expression be ‘solved?’”, 2024, Align to Innovate

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